

Taxol is NOT produced sustainably by endophytic fungi ! – A case study for the damage that scientific papermills can cause for the scientific communities

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ABSTRACT

Over three decades ago, the plant-derived anticancer agent taxol (brand name: paclitaxel) was reported from a fungal endophyte colonizing the producing plant. The hope that this finding could ever result in a sustainable production process has thus far been disappointed. Modern evidence on the evolution of secondary metabolites in plants vs. fungi suggests that this hypothesis (that fungi could produce such complex plant metabolites) is invalid. Still, numerous inconclusive original studies -and in particular, review papers by non-experts in the field- are continuously being published that claim the opposite. The current commentary tries to deal with the topic, taking the findings of -OMICS studies and current state-of-the-art mycology into account. This can hopefully help to stop the scientific papermills from further spreading the fake news that fungi were capable of sustainable production of taxol.

The current paper treats a phenomenon that has been discussed rather controversially throughout the past decades. It concerns the production of secondary metabolites that were originally reported from plants by endophytic fungi derived from surface-disinfected tissues of the plants that contain the respective secondary metabolites. This phenomenon was first explored for the anticancer agent taxol (paclitaxel) in traces by a fungal “endophyte” that was concurrently even given its own genus name, “*Taxomyces andreanae*” (Stierle et al., 1993; Strobel et al., 1993).

In order to clarify the taxonomy of *Taxomyces*, we recently analyzed the genome of the type strain, which had resulted from the study by Heinig et al. (2013), in a failed attempt to detect the key biosynthetic genes coding for taxol in the “*Taxomyces*” genome (cf Cheng et al., 2022). Genome mining for salient phylogenetic marker loci and a concurrent microscopic examination of the holotype specimen, deposited in the Farlow Herbarium at Harvard University (FH), revealed that this fungus represents a basidiomycete, belonging to *Ceriporiopsis*, a genus of wood-destroying polypores. Therefore, “*Taxomyces andreanae*” is now classified as *Ceriporiopsis andreanae*.

The paper by Cheng et al. (2022) has already received multiple citations, but we are not proud of all of them. We fear that some of the

authors who cited our work may actually not have read the text (and in particular the discussion!), very carefully. They even used our study as additional proof that taxol was a fungal metabolite. For the sake of clarity, **some text passages of the original papers** that cited our work are quoted in “**bold parentheses**” below, and we comment on them afterwards (**we have intentionally left the original text in bold face, so the readership can make up their own minds about the scrutiny of the review process!**).

For instance, Rai et al. (2023) who cited various (unconfirmed) sources among the genus *Phoma* as taxol producers, have cited us in the following sentence “**Group *Phoma sensu lato* represents a reliable source of secondary metabolites and can be explored both genetically and physico-chemically to surge yields of anticipated metabolites and to harvest novel analogs of active compounds**”. - In fact, we did not even mention the genus (not: group!) *Phoma* in our IMA Fungus paper (Cheng et al., 2022), which most certainly did not refer to the topics expressed in that sentence.

Subban and Kempken (2023), on the other hand, dared to cite our paper without giving any further comment in a table where they summarized the known cases for successful detection of taxol biosynthetic genes in fungi! In their Table 1, entitled “Analysis of next-generation

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sequencing for “the discovering putative Taxol biosynthetic genes from Taxol producing endophytic fungi” they listed our paper as “Fungal sp. EF0021” from *Taxus* spp. with 454 GS FLX titanium” as sequencing method and claimed we had actually detected a “Terpene synthase”!. As stated above, we did not generate any new data at all. We did indeed use the 454 sequence from the very conclusive paper by Heinig et al. (2013), where the “terpene synthetase” (!) was not detected at all, using a fairly advanced methodology. It remains obscure why the latter paper by Heinig et al. (2013), which should have been much more important to cite than our more recent study on their data, has not been cited by Subban and Kempken (2023) at all. Regardless of the validity of the citations, we think that such review papers on important topics should always discuss the Pros as well as the Cons and not just ignore valuable contributions by capable researchers who have found results that deviate from any initially established hypothesis.

Yu et al. (2023) also cited our paper in the following sentence: “The terpenoid paclitaxel produced by the endophytic fungus *Taxomyces andreanae* is recognized today as the broad-spectrum antitumor drug”! - This is clearly not a correct citation of our paper, because the authors should have referred to *Ceriporiopsis andreanae*. After all, this was the major point of the study by Cheng et al. (2022).

It is difficult to understand why these papers were accepted by highly renowned ISI journals that are supposed to have established a rigorous peer-review system. On the other hand, we were happy to see that our paper has been cited in the appropriate context in the review by Prescott et al. (2023), indicating that at least some of our colleagues who cited our work (Cheng et al., 2022) more carefully and drew the appropriate conclusions.

The above citations of our recent paper caused us to consider whether we may have failed to express our opinion about the fungal taxol production explicitly enough. Many of the scientific articles about fungal taxol that were published in the past were likewise not in accordance to high ethics of scientific standards. Even numerous reviews that treat the discovery of genuine fungal metabolites from fungal endophytes started with the questionable discovery of taxol in their introduction. The authors of the first papers about the detection of taxol in a fungal culture are actually not to be blamed for that. At the time they published their results, it may actually have been plausible that a fungus can produce taxol. They even went at length to use immunochemistry methods to detect the compound in the fungal culture because they were probably desperate to prove their hypothesis. Nowadays, we know that such methodology is inappropriate for detection of fungal secondary metabolites. We would like to refer to Pfütze et al. (2024) for an realistic example on what is needed to exploit the full dimensions of fungal secondary metabolism more realistically.

To avoid further mis-citations of our work, we here discuss this matter without the taxonomic context of Cheng et al. (2022). We provide some solid arguments why we think that the study of endophytes for production of taxol and other complex plant metabolites is not an attractive research goal to follow up.

1. Taxol and related compounds are chemotaxonomic markers for a certain group of gymnosperms. Neither angiosperms nor other members of the Kingdom Plantae have ever been shown unquestionably to produce any remotely similar metabolites. There are some highly tentative publications that reported the compound from angiosperms like *Corylus*, but neither of them has ever led to any substantial findings that proved, e.g. the biosynthetic genes or the precursors to be present in the plants or their DNA, respectively. We do not even bother to cite such reports because this would be out of the scope of the current commentary. Fungi, on which we would like to focus here, are now known to have diverged during the evolution of organisms very early and constitute their own kingdom (Katz et al., 2012). Therefore, it is inconceivable that taxol production could have been inherited in the course of evolutionary processes.

2. Taxol biosynthesis follows a complicated route that has until today still not be fully understood. It is clear that the biosynthesis genes encoding its production are incoherent and **not arranged in a gene cluster** as is the case with the biosynthesis of many fungal metabolites (Cox, 2024). As stated by Heinig et al. (2013), this fact alone makes the frequently postulated “horizontal gene transfer” (HGT) between *Taxus* and its fungal endophytes highly improbable, if not impossible. Nevertheless, many research groups have not realized this hard fact and sought for homologous genes from the plant taxol biosynthetic pathway in fungi. The subsequent discovery of even one gene among the numerous necessary ones was then often considered as diagnostic marker for taxol production. However, the yew taxol biosynthetic pathway comprises around 19 enzymatic steps (Walker and Croteau, 2001). Finding of the homologue of the first gene in the pathway, encoding taxa-4(5),11(12)-diene synthase (TS) was reported in several fungi (El-Sayed et al., 2019, 2020; Miao et al., 2009; Staniek et al., 2009), but we did not find the corresponding DNA sequences of any of these enzymes in GenBank or other public domain databases. Despite a very diligent search, we failed to find a single study that published TS gene sequences from fungi. The only published fungal genes with confirmed (but tentative) similarities to the *Taxus* taxol pathway are those encoding 10-deacetylbaconin III-10-O-acetyl transferase (dbat) found in *Aspergillus*, *Cladosporium* and *Fusarium* (Zhang et al. 2009, Zhang et al., 2009b, Chakravarthi et al., 2020; Sah et al., 2017). The above examples certainly do not reflect the whole dimension of this phenomenon, on which we are going to come back further below when we discuss the analytics. Finally, the probability of HGT has not been confirmed by whole-genome sequencing studies either, as none of them found homologies to the taxol biosynthetic pathway in plants (Miao et al., 2018; Qiao et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2014).

Interestingly, the fungi in question have never been subjected to a decent taxonomic study and are often not deposited in a public domain collection. Curiously, the authors went at length to sequence all the putative proteins that presumably encode for secondary metabolite biosynthesis, but only included ITS sequences and not even rudimentary morphological data. In most of the aforementioned genera it is absolutely not possible to make an identification at the species level based on such data, so even the species names given in the titles are questionable.

3. Taxol is a very potent inhibitor of beta-tubulin, a protein that constitutes an essential component of all Eukaryotes. **Therefore, the compound also shows rather strong antifungal and phytotoxic activities.** A fungus that has acquired the ability to produce taxol would thus concurrently have needed to develop a specific mechanism (e.g., to remove the toxin from its cells) that requires additional energy and/ or have specific enzymes for “detoxification”. On the other hand, an endophytic fungus that wastes its resources for production of a general toxin will inadvertently lose part of its competitiveness, unless there are other advantages involved. There is a famous example on convergent biosynthesis of gibberellins in plants vs. their fungal *Fusarium* pathogens, where it is evident that the pathogenic fungus can gain a selective advantage by biosynthesizing the phytohormone. The gibberellins do not have prominent antifungal activities, but they heavily interfere with the physiology of the host plant and thereby make it easier to overcome the host plant’s immune system (Tudzynski, 2005). Therefore, it makes perfect sense for the fungi to evolve such a metabolic pathway convergently and spend the necessary energy to produce the compound.
4. At least the horizontally transmitted (Class 3) endophytes are normally “dormant”, i.e. they are sitting in the tissues of their host plants and do not differentiate much. If a fungus biosynthesized a secondary metabolite in the host plant, it would need to supply itself with the necessary energy. This additional energy could come from the host

plant, by direct nutrient supply. The alternative, i.e., the digestion of the plant tissue by the endophyte, would result in its becoming a pathogen! It is hard to conceive that endophytic fungi can produce any metabolites at all *in planta*, unless the hosts themselves would gain an advantage. There are some examples where this is the case, which concern vertically transmitted (Class 1) endophytes like *Epichloë* species (Schardl, 2001) or the mutualistic rugulosin- and swainsonine-producing ascomycetes that produce feeding deterrents, by which they act beneficially to their hosts (Creamer and Baucom, 2013; Sumarah et al., 2008).

5. In most studies dealing with fungi that allegedly produce complex plant metabolites (not only including taxane diterpenoids, but also other secondary metabolites that were never isolated from fungi), the strains have been incubated at random on complex media and not even a time course of production was recorded. The employed detection methods ranged from HPLC-DAD to HPLC-MS, and only in rare cases did the authors use an authentic standard. There is to our knowledge not a single case where the authors actually did the right thing to verify their tentative detection of the target compound: make a scale-up fermentation, isolate the target compound to purity and then measure NMR spectra of the purified metabolite. Such procedures are well-established (and essential!) in the natural product community and have led to the discovery of thousands of genuine, new fungal metabolites. In our current line of work, which involves the discovery of genuine, novel natural products from fungi, we are constantly being asked by competent reviewers who ask us for proof about the absolute configurations of our molecules, in order to get the respective papers accepted. This can never be achieved by mere HPLC analytics.
6. It is difficult for us to conceive why (to our knowledge) almost nobody has ever attempted such preparative work with the aforementioned fungi when a peak that resembled taxol was detected in a fungal crude extract. We have come across some studies where NMR data are actually depicted, but the respective manuscripts have certain flaws. For instance, Chakravarthi et al. (2020) showed both, MS and NMR spectra from taxol and baccatin-3 and claimed that they derived from the fungal culture. The taxol spectrum shown that was said to be derived from the crude extract has a similar purity as the standard. However, their description only includes analytical procedures by which they detected the compound. No purification of the compound was described. In fact, it is impossible to gain such NMR data as the authors showed from crude extracts. Production of substantial quantities of crude material are necessary to purify mg amounts of the respective molecules, prior to NMR measurements. We suspect that the authors have omitted important experimental procedures in their manuscript, but the readership is free to think about possible alternatives themselves ... Frankly, we are not absolutely sure whether genuine data have been reported.

The above cited study by Yang et al. (2014), which was accepted by a journal devoted to genomics, did report an isolation procedure and even included NMR spectra, even though no yields during the isolation were reported as would be regarded mandatory for papers in chemical journals. The *Penicillium* sp. they were working on was obtained from *Corylus*, rather than *Taxus*. Regarding the large numbers of papers on the topic, which demonstrate a rather high interest of the scientific community, we are puzzled that now, even ten years after the paper by Yang et al. (2014) was published, no other research group has been able to reproduce their results, followed up on them and published another paper.

The initial motivation in the 1990s to check the endophytes for taxol production was a shortage for the anticancer drug. Initially, there had been concerns about the sustainability of supply because taxol needed to be isolated from the bark of *Taxus brevifolia*, which is a very slow growing tree that cannot easily be cultivated. Meanwhile two different alternatives have been established to avoid any shortage: using *Taxus*

cell cultures for large scale biotechnological production (Expósito et al., 2009) or extraction of the compounds from needles of different *Taxus* species like the European *Taxus baccata* and subsequent semi-synthesis (Holton et al., 1995). The establishment of both procedures has taken the pharmaceutical industry a long time, substantial investments were necessary to reach the goal, and the costs of goods are still rather high. Even though normally negative results are not being published, in particular by industrial companies, it is inconceivable to assume that Big Pharma would not have followed up on the matter with fungal endophytes as potential, alternative sources. We assume that many of the companies have tried but failed because they could not develop a sustainable process based on fungal fermentation. It was described by Staniek et al. (2009) that the "*Taxomyces*" did not produce any taxol. The only pharmaceutical drug for use in humans derived from a fungal endophyte that has made it to the market is to our knowledge the antimycotic Ibrexafungerp, a semisynthetic derivative of enfumafungin. This is a genuine fungal metabolite whose biosynthesis genes in the producers of the genus *Hormonema* are also known (Kuhnert et al., 2018).

1. Conclusion

There are many other arguments that were recently summarized by non-specialists in a very concise manner (Gärditz and Cesnick, 2023). These authors brought the story of taxol production in a relation to the problem of maintaining scientific integrity. They criticized the endless papermills, which resulted in unreflected citations of reviews that cite other reviews, but fail to recognize the value of concise studies like that of Heinig et al. (2013) and Staniek et al. (2009), who reported negative results.

The interest in taxol from yew endophytes was based from the beginning on the erroneous assumption that yew endophytes would have a greater capacity for taxol production, and more likely HGT, than any other fungi. The endophytes in question are Class 3 endophytes, which, unlike Class 1 endophytes, are not transmitted vertically (via seeds) but horizontally. They are not host specific and live in a wide range of plants. The endophytic stage constitutes only one of their life stages, and they are commonly found as saprotrophs in soil or on plant debris. The reason why it pays off to attempt to isolate them is that they comprise many slow-growing species that are more easily accessible from the surface-disinfected plant tissue than from soil and debris. Although they may have some mutualistic relationships with the host tree, there is no evidence of any coevolution. Incidentally, studies screening non-endophytic fungi take a wide "capture" of taxol. This is just to appeal to the fact that there is no reason to believe that these fungi have more biotechnological potential than other fungi.

Zhang et al. (2023) recently published an excellent paper, in which they reconstructed important elements of the taxol biosynthesis in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, based on methods of synthetic biology. Maybe this avenue of work is ultimately going to result in the first sustainable production of taxol by a fungus, but we are already afraid that some ignorant authors of forthcoming papers are soon going to call the Bakers Yeast a "fungal endophyte".

We hope that this article can finally stop the researchers who are working on fungal endophytes (and in particular, the supervisors of young students!) from reaching a dead end because there are many other interesting aspects of applied mycology that need to be tackled in the future. We also would like to warn the readership of this article not to believe everything that has been written in the scientific literature. Particular care must be taken in cases where the original sources cannot be found but there are dozens of reviews that just cite other reviews and do not present any original work.

Declaration of competing interest

We hereby declare no conflict of interest as also stated in the

manuscript text. This is an invited commentary after all!

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